

METHODS OF FORMING STUDENTS' INTEREST IN EXAMPLES OF BOOKS

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Abstract: Reading plays an important role in a student's life. Artistic with the help of reading interest in literature arises. The works of art read in childhood remain in the mind of a person for a long time remains sealed and ensures his spiritual-intellectual development. Fiction examples help students to form norms of behavior. High moral and examples of fiction as an important pedagogical tool in the formation of a spiritual person serves.

Key words: concept, education, methods, books, process, interesting.

Curriculum, educational concept and standard that make up the educational content, tools such as programs, textbooks, methodical manuals are coordinated with the teacher only if the training evening will be effective. Because the meaning of the educational process directly depends on the personality of the teacher, his level, knowledge and skills depends. It is the student who realizes the changes in the society and the educational process and the teacher who directly faces. It's no secret that I have a general education more than twenty academic subjects are studied in their schools. Most of them are direct students directed to the goal of developing thinking, imparting knowledge. Some subjects serve to teach a child professionally.

Among the academic subjects, only literature belongs directly to the child it is a means of perfecting his mind, spirit and spirituality. Literature lessons are not for the formation of specialists, but for the education of the individual's spirituality does. Therefore, in the process of literary education, it is not necessary to provide knowledge from pure literary studies, but it is desirable that the education of the human heart should be a priority. In literature classes in the process of analyzing the works of art and discussing the actions of the characters students learn the secrets of man and the universe, the author of the work and literary heroes they discover a person in the form of a person, and in the end, the ordinary citizen begins to realize his identity. A person who realizes his identity and has an independent point of view, others decide his fate will not allow him to do so.

Literary games in the formation of students' interest in examples of works of art and literary evenings are important. Artistic games can be organized as follows:

- games and exercises aimed at developing students' speech;
- artistic puzzles;
- art quizzes;
- games based on a certain style¹

¹ Mingbaeva B. Methods and techniques of forming interest in examples of fiction in primary school students through reading. International conference on innovations in

Various events are organized in cooperation with cultural institutions: library hours, trips to museums, participation in exhibitions, reader contests participation, staging of fairy tales, etc. And in the organization of literature classes, the student is considered as a person with a noble spirit the following principles of education are leading for formation: - lesson plan change. According to this, the lessons are in the traditional way, that is, the organizational part, homework asking and strengthening it, new lesson statement and strengthening it, giving homework is not implemented in this way. The lesson is based on a new work presented in the program while working, relying on the students' previous knowledge and life experiences asking controversial questions and ensuring students' independent work based on.

In learners based on the orientation of reading lessons primarily to the personality of the student opportunities to form interest in the examples of artistic works will be expanded. That's it Pedagogical tools, methods and methods serving this purpose are presented.

They are:

1. Method of personal experience activation. In this, the teacher works for the students offers to enter the situation of the characters. In this process, students their personal lives select specific situations related to Have students write about their feelings and experiences and will be asked to compare with their classmates.
2. the method of introspective analysis is unique in teaching artistic works to students is a method. Certain situations are always described in works of art. These situations related to human life. Human experiences are expressed in it and enter the reader's heart goes One of the tasks of the teacher is to express his personal experiences to the students is to set the task.
3. Person-oriented theatrical method. This method students consists of interest in a theatrical work of art. In this place, the students have a work of art creating interest, staging a work of art in awakening their feelings the use of elements is considered. Using this method, students create a work of art they feel the feelings and experiences of the hero.
4. Method of self-creative expression. Students culture using this method imagine their place in the world. To do this, the teacher gives the students a variety of choices, stage should be prepared for proper participation in appearances.
5. the connection of teaching with life. Life lessons in traditional education it is the teacher's duty to ensure the relevance. The student's moral In lessons aimed at perfection, the concept of science based on life events and they themselves absorb its laws, they return from theory to life.
6. giving tasks to the student for independent activity. Literary education In this principle of organization, asking for homework can be done in groups or in groups is carried out by execution in the form Pupils to master a new subject achieves tasks independently, i.e. by working hard.

Independent works are presented creatively or semi-creatively. A short one that takes 3-4 minutes term independent work also activates students; - individualization of education. Individualization of the process of school literature lessons is a gap in knowledge acquisition

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to prevent it from happening, as much as possible with each of the students consists of working. When working with each student individually, his/her individual characteristics, uniqueness in knowledge acquisition, memory, level of acquisition, character and interests must be taken into account.

Acquaintance of students with a work of art in literature classes allows them to get acquainted with high moral and spiritual values, to educate the needs in this field. Teaching students to work on art means providing education by forming and growing the skills of literary-aesthetic analysis in them. The analysis of a work of art is to retrace the creative path of the writer in the process of creating that work, to share the thoughts, feelings and conclusions of the author, at the same time to be inspired by his achievements, to express a critical reaction to his shortcomings. Literary analysis requires creativity, pedagogical skills, self-sacrifice from the teacher in organizing students' activities, enriching their knowledge and directing it to a specific goal.

Literature reflects life. At the same time, it is a special form of understanding, a means of understanding the truth. The task of literature is not limited to this. It gives a new meaning to life and has an impact. In order to explain this to the students, in the process of analysis, general information is given about the subject taking a certain form in the work of art. When the reader gets acquainted with the content of the work during reading, he turns to its poetics during analysis. While reading enriches the senses and sharpens the mind, analysis helps to delve deeper into the meaning behind the text.

The student will not only study a specific work through analysis, but will also get acquainted with the laws related to artistic creativity in various fields such as literature, logic, linguistics, psychology, didactics, art philosophy. To achieve this, the teacher should solve the following issues: 1. Determine the purpose and content of the analysis. 2. Organization of work (distribution of the analysis of the work by lessons, development of a system of assignments). 3. Determining the range of skills acquired by students on the basis of which methods the text is studied. Literary aesthetic analysis is unique according to the genre characteristics of each work, the age, knowledge and skills of students. For example, if a riddle is mastered by comparing the similarities between the subject and events, the content of the articles will be understandable only if they are interpreted with the help of real life examples.

The human life, personal society of the book its incomparable role in spiritual development has been known since ancient times. He knows the world, gives knowledge together with instilling a love of beauty, delighting in it, hating evil develops the feeling. A book is a reader's understanding of the world. In addition to providing support, its scientific forms a worldview, forms a positive character, how to solve life and life conflicts teaches. Anyone who possesses these qualities a student is a highly spiritual person matures. After all, the book is a spiritual heritage that strengthens the chain of generations. It is the human spirit influences and leads them to spiritual and moral perfection, affects their emotions and pleasure to the reader while imparting knowledge dedicates and sharpens the mind and educates it. Literary critic Safo Matjonov noted, "Scientific works are from ignorance and ignorance. if it saves, the works of art will get rid of rudeness and shame. Both this and that enlightened, happy people is absolutely useful and necessary for²

² Matjonov S. Independent works from literature at school (methodical guide for the teacher.). - T.: "Teacher", 1996. - p. 37

In forming the culture of reading in students, the teacher has scientific and popular, reading, reading artistic, historical works should be followed in terms of instilling love for reading and raising the level of reading We would like to recommend the following criteria:

- what kind of books students should read determine the level of interest and thinking;
- understanding of the student's thinking activities, freely with members of the community focus on developing communication skills and competencies;
- able to express one's opinion fluently and freely skill formation;
- reading books by reading works of interest and asking for their content learn to keep a diary in this place;
- developing the ability to express written speech signs in pronunciation, to read text expressively.

A book especially for teenage readers it is important to develop interest in reading and reading. Because it is age students feel very free, lively begins to notice the events around him interest increases. They are more themselves interest activity secretly from adults tries to do. lying, to hide his guilt and in front of adults tries to pretend to be sane. How do students of this age spend their free time? What are you doing? parents, teachers, coaches, neighborhood activists are always in control must.

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